

MYANMAR WEB PAGES CRAWLER

Su Mon Khine, Yadana Thein

University of Computer Studies, Yangon

ABSTRACT

Nowadays web pages are implemented in various kinds of languages on the Web and web crawlers are important for search engine. Language specific crawlers are crawlers that traverse and collect the relative web pages using the successive URLs of web page. There are very few research areas in crawling for Myanmar Language web sites. Most of the language specific crawlers are based on n-gram character sequences which require training documents. The proposed crawler differs from those crawlers. The proposed crawler searches and retrieves Myanmar web pages for Myanmar Language search engine. The proposed crawler detects the Myanmar character and rule-based syllable threshold is used to judgment the relevance of the pages. According to experimental results, the proposed crawler has better performance, achieves successful accuracy and storage space for search engines are lesser since it only crawls the relevant documents for Myanmar web sites.

KEYWORDS

Language specific crawler, Myanmar Language, rule-based syllable segmentation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Internet provides valuable resources of all types and web area is grown exponentially day by day. Web pages are added by different site holders every time. Gathering the web pages manually for language specific search engines is not possible and realistic. Therefore search engines mainly rely on crawlers to create and maintain indices for the web pages. Web crawlers are short software codes also called wanderers, automatic indexers, Web robots, Web spiders, ants, bots, Web scatters [2]. To collect the set Myanmar Web pages for search engine, crawlers, which traverses the Web by following the hyperlinks and stored the download pages in a repository and used then by indexer component to index the web pages, are needed.

In comparison to general purpose crawlers which traverse all the pages on the Web, language specific crawlers are collected only for specific languages on the Web. Most of the language specific crawlers were implemented using n-gram character sequences to detect language, encoding schemes and scripts of training corpus, which is the basic method for text categorization and required trained documents in prior to classify language of web pages[7]. Some researchers detected language of web pages on Urls of top domain. Eda BayKan, Monka Henzinger, Ingmar Weber [5] determined the language of web pages using its URL of the country code of the top level domain by using machine learning classifiers such as Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree, Relative Entropy, Maximum Entropy and experimented English, German, French, Spanish and Italian Languages. Takayuki Tamura, Kulwadee Somboonviwat and Masaru Kitsuregawa [8] identified language of the Thai web pages by content type of HTML META tag firstly. If the content types are missed, checked then the content of web pages based on TextCat, a language guesser based on n-gram statistics. Myanmar web pages cannot detect exactly language of web pages by checking the character set of HTML META tags since most of the web sites developers are not definitely identified for Myanmar character set in META tag. Furthermore, web pages cannot identify its languages by using Urls of top domain since Myanmar languages web pages are mostly

distributed on other top level domain such as .com, .info, .net rather than .mm which is referred to Myanmar country. Therefore this proposed system relies on content of web pages for crawling in order to download the Myanmar web pages and the judgment of relevancy is easily determined by proposed rule-based syllable percentage thresholds. The crawling process in this system is based on crawler4j[1] and extends the crawler to collect only Myanmar web pages for further process of web search engine for Myanmar Language.

This paper is organized into seven sections. Literature reviews are discussed in the next section. Section 3 describes various types of crawlers and some open source general web crawlers. Myanmar scripts, fonts and encoding on web are explained in Section 4. Section 5 describes the proposed crawler. Experimental results will be discussed in Section 6 and proposed system will be concluded in Section 7.

2. LITERATURE REVIEWS

In this section, the topics related to this proposed crawler are discussed. AltaVista search engine introduced a crawling module named as Mercator [4], which was scalable for searching the entire Web and extensible. Olena Medelyan, Stefan Schulz, Jan Paetzold, Michael Poprar, Kornel Marko , [6] used n-gram model for text categorization tool based on content of web pages using standard crawler Nutch and checked the domain of web pages with training documents collections. Dr Rajender Nath and Khyati Chopra [2] discussed about the Web Crawlers: Taxonomy, Issues & Challenges. They classified the crawlers according to coverage areas, mobility, topic –domain and load distribution to Unfocused and Focused Crawler , Mobility Based Crawler , Domain specific crawler and Based on Load Intra and Distributed Crawler respectively. They also discussed issues of Crawlers. The proposed crawler is related to Domain (Specific) crawler because it does not need to collect the entire Web, but needs to retrieve and collect only Myanmar Web pages. Finally, the relevance to the web page is determined by rule-based the syllable percentage threshold.

3. VARIOUS TYPES OF CRAWLERS AND SOME OPEN SOURCE CRAWLERS

This section describes different types of crawlers and some open source crawlers. Trupti V. Udapure1, Ravindra D. Kale, Rajesh C. Dharmik [3] discussed four different types of web crawlers: **(1) Focused web crawler** : Focused Crawler is the crawler that tries to download the pages which are related to a specific and relevant of a topic that users interest. **(2) Incremental crawler**: In order to refresh the download pages, crawlers replace the old documents with newly downloaded documents frequently based on the estimate of how often pages changes. **(3) Distributed crawler**: Different crawlers are working in distributed forms in order to download the most coverage of the web, in which central crawler manages all other distributed crawlers. **(4) Parallel Crawler**: Many crawlers ran in parallel and a parallel crawler consists of multiple crawling processes and it may be local or distributed at geographically distance location. In addition to another, some of the general open source web crawlers that are widely used today is also listed in Table 1.

Table1. Some of the general open source Web crawlers.

Types of Crawlers	Definition
Web SPHINX , WebLech	Website-Specific for HTML Information extraction.
Nutch, Crawler4j, JSpider, Heritrix	Highly configurable, extensible and customizable open source Web Spider.
WebEater, HttpTrack ,Web-Harvest	Web site retrieval and offline viewing.
JoBo ,Arachnid ,Java Web crawler	Simple Web spider.

Figure2. Structure of Myanmar Syllable

4.1 Different fonts and encoding system for Myanmar Web sites.

The first generation of Myanmar encoding systems were ASCII code in which Latin English glyphs were replaced by the Myanmar script glyphs to render the Myanmar script which was no standardization of encoding characters. Firstly, Myanmar script was added to Unicode Consortium in 1999 as version 3.0 and improved Unicode5.1 in 2008 and Myanmar3, Padauk and Parabaik fonts are in the range of U+1000 to U+109F. And then, various fonts such as Myazedi, Zawgyi-One have been created. Although Zawgyi-One is not Unicode standard, over 90% of Web sites use Zawgyi-One font. Unicode stores text in only one order and render correctly. Zawgyi-One can store text in several ways but superficially appears correct. Therefore, the proposed crawler converts all fonts to Zawgyi-One fonts and normalizes various writing style to one standard style. For example, the user can write ' ' ' ' or ' ' ' ' after writing consonant ' ' for syllable ' ' that is equivalent to 'Ko' in English. Table 3 shows different encoding sequences of Unicode and Zawgyi-One and Table 4 shows some examples of normalization of Zawgyi-One character.

Table 3. Sequence style of using Unicode and Zawgyi-One for Myanmar Syllable

Fonts	Sequence Style
Unicode	+ + =
	+ + =
Zawgyi-One	+ + =
	+ + =

Table 4. Normalization of Zawgyi-One character sequences.

Various forms of writing sequence	Normalize sequence
- / -	-
- / -	-
- / -	-
- / - / - / -	-
- / - / - / -	-
- / - / - / - / - / -	-
.....
- / - / - / -	-

5. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE FOR PROPOSED CRAWLER

The proposed crawler traverses identified famous Myanmar web sites seeds URLs systematically, it identifies all Urls containing in the page and adds them to the frontier, which contains the list of unvisited URLs. URLs from the frontier are visited one by one, fetch the web pages and parse the pages to parser to remove HTML tags in order to check Myanmar character. The proposed crawler normalizes various fonts to Zawgyi-One font since Zawgyi-One is mainly dominant fonts on Web pages. After normalization, the proposed crawler calculates the syllable threshold based on rule-based syllable identification in order to judgment the relevance of the pages. If the web pages are relevant, store them in the pages repository in order to ready for indexer to extract the keywords of web pages. The process is repeated until the crawling process reaches the specified depth of the crawler after starting from the specified seeds URLs. Figure3 shows the design of proposed crawler and Figure 4 shows the process flow of proposed crawler.

Figure3. The design of proposed crawler

1. Put the Myanmar web sites URLs to the crawler as seed URLs.
 2. Check for stopping criteria.
 3. If the specified criterion is not reached, add URLs to the Work Queue.
 4. Pick the URL up from the Work Queue.
 5. Fetch the web pages and pass them to parser in order to extract the content.
 6. Detect Myanmar character of the range between the decimal values of 4096 to 4255 defined by Unicode Consortium.
 7. Normalize various fonts to Zawgyi-One font.
 8. Identify the relevant of Myanmar Web pages by proposed rule base syllable thresholds.
 9. Extract the Urls, add them to the Frontier and store the pages in repository.
 7. Otherwise, discard the web pages.
- Go to Step 2 and repeat when the specified depth is reached.

Figure4. Process flow of proposed crawler.

5.1. Proposed rule-based syllable segmentation

After detecting Myanmar characters and normalization to one standard font, the system devices Myanmar sentences into syllables by the proposed rule-based syllable segmentation methods and calculates threshold in order to identify the relevant of Myanmar Pages since Myanmar Web pages are mixed with other languages. The proposed rule-based syllable segmentation method is shown in Figure 5. The proposed crawler does not considered the spelling checking of syllables since it only segments the content of web pages.

1. If we found one consonant and next character is not '□' or any consonant then take one syllable by combining the rest of characters until we found any consonants or '□' or '□'
2. If starting character is '□' or '□' and next character is consonants, take one syllable by combining the rest of character until we found another consonants or '□' or '□'
3. If first character is '□' and second character is '□' and next character is consonant, take one syllable by combining the rest of characters until we found another consonant or '□' or '□'

Figure5. Proposed rule-based syllable segmentation method

Some of the Myanmar Web sites are mixed with other languages. For the combination of Myanmar and other language documents, Myanmar content which exceeds the predefined syllable threshold will be considered as relevant of Myanmar Web pages and stores them into page repository in order to further study of word segmentation and below the threshold will be discard as a non relevant pages to save storage space on disk. Threshold percentage is calculated by the ratio of Myanmar Syllable count to the total numbers of Myanmar Syllable and other characters contained in that web pages. Figure 6 and 7 show example of web pages combined with other languages such as English Languages.

Figure 6. Greater threshold of Myanmar Syllable to other language

Figure7. Fewer threshold of Myanmar Syllable to other language

According to Figure 6, the proposed crawler can crawl 82% of Myanmar syllable percentage threshold to other language character and Figure 7 shows the proposed crawler can crawl 2.5% of Myanmar syllable to other languages such as English language. The proposed crawler will regard Figure 6 as relevant pages and store in pages repository and Figure 7 will be discard in order to reduce storage space in repository when syllable threshold is set to 3%. In this proposed crawler, users can easily define syllable percentage thresholds depends on how much percentage of Myanmar language web pages to other language they want. It can easily to define and scalable.

6. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

6.1 Performance Evaluation

The evaluation methodology commonly and widely used in information retrieval is to calculate the precision. In the language specific crawling prospective, precision represents the ratio of the number of language relevant documents to the total number downloaded documents. Precision also called “harvest rate” in equation 1 is used for major performance metric for language specific crawler community.

$$\text{Precision (Harvest rate)} = \frac{\text{Language relevant pages}}{\text{Total download pages}} \quad (1)$$

6.2 Crawling experiment

In this section, the proposed crawler presents the result of experiment of crawler. The proposed crawler was started with 11 Myanmar web site seeds URLs shown in Table 5, which are popular Myanmar Web sites. We crawled two times for 32 bit operating system, 4GB memory with different internet downloads speed at day and night respectively. The first run of the crawler at 9: AM to 2: PM with the depth of crawler is set to 7 and Myanmar syllable threshold is set to 4% ,8960 Html Myanmar documents were download .The second run of the crawler at 1: AM to 5: AM with the depth of crawler is set to 10 and Myanmar syllable threshold is set to 3% ,12582 HTML documents were downloaded. In total, 21542 documents were collected in this system and the results are shown in table 6. The result shows that fewer percent of syllable thresholds can download more documents and greater percent of syllable threshold can download fewer documents.

Table 5. Myanmar web site seeds Urls

No	Urls	Description
1	http://www.president-office.gov.mm/	Information
2	http://my.wikipedia.org/wiki/.mm	Information
3	http://www.thithtolwin.com	News
4	http://www.7days.com	News
5	http://www.myanmarwebdesigner.com/blog/	Technology
6	http://winthumon.blogspot.com/2010/03/valueable-words.html	Literature
7	http://www.rfa.org/burmese/	News
8	http://hivinfo4mm.org/category/myanmar/	Health
9	http://www.myanmar-network.net/	Education
10	http://www.oppositeyes.info/	Politics
11	http://burmese.dvb.no/dvblive	News

Table 6. Different runs of crawler

	Depth of crawler	Syllable threshold	Total pages downloaded
First run	7	4	8960
Second run	10	3	12582
Total			21542

It is a little difficult to calculate the precision of all download documents manually, the proposed crawler only calculates for first 1300 pages of each run. For the first run of crawler, by manually checking the relevancy of Myanmar pages ,1289 pages of 1300 were correctly downloaded as Myanmar web pages and only 24 pages were download incorrectly and we achieved the precision was 98.15%. For the second run of the crawler, 1294 pages of 1300 were correctly download as Myanmar web pages and only 15 pages were download incorrectly and we achieved the precision was 98.84%. The experiments also evaluated that the proposed crawler

outperformed n-gram based language identification which require sufficient training corpus for different fonts and encoding. The proposed crawler does not necessary training corpus and easily identify as Myanmar Language web site. Table 7 shows the average percentage of precision for proposed crawler and ngram-based crawler which were 98.49 % and 96.6% respectively.

Table 7. Precision of the proposed crawler and n-gram based crawler

	Proposed crawler		N-gram Based Crawler	
	First run	Second run	First run	Second run
Correctly download as Myanmar pages	1289	1294	1192	1268
Incorrectly download as Myanmar pages	11	6	108	32
No of pages	1300	1300	1300	1300
Accuracy	99.15%	99.53%	91.69	97.54
Average Accuracy	99.34%		94.6%	

The crawler analyzed what kinds of top level domains are influenced on Myanmar Web sites. The average percentage of top level domains for Myanmar web sites in which the crawler downloaded are.com 83.08%, .mm 7% .org 5.2%, .net 3.24%, .info 0.92% and other for 0.56 respectively are shown in Figure 8.

Figure8. Influence of different domains on Myanmar web sites.

The crawler also analyzed which fonts are mostly used for Myanmar web sites for each domain. Among them, Zawgyi-One font was the widely used for web developer and Myanmar3 was the secondly used on Myanmar web site especially on governmental sites. Win Innwa was the thirdly used and the most rarely font was Padauk on Myanmar web sites according to the results. Table 8 shows the fonts usage for each domain and Figure 9 shows bar chat representation for each font on each domain.

Table 8. Various fonts for each domain

	Zawgyi-One	Win Innwa	Myanmar3	Padauk	Total
.com	82.3	7.0	9.0	1.7	100%
.mm	76.5	2.0	20.0	1.5	100%
.org	87.4	4.0	7.6	1.0	100%
.net	86.0	4.0	9.3	0.7	100%
.info	92.7	4	3	0.3	100%
other	92.9	2	5	0.1	100%

Figure.9 various fonts for each domain.

7. CONCLUSION

We propose language specific crawler in order to retrieve and download the Myanmar web pages for the supporting of web search engine for Myanmar Language. Myanmar characters of Web pages are detected and the relevant judgment of the web pages is determined by the proposed rule-based syllable percentage threshold. This crawler can easily adjust the Myanmar syllable threshold in order to judge the relevance to the pages. The proposed crawler can download various fonts written in web pages. This crawler also analyzes the various kinds of domains in Myanmar Language web sites and different fonts types for each domain. According to statistic, Zawgyi-One is the most influence on web pages and other fonts are fewer used on web pages. The proposed system is implemented in java language that is easy to install, develop, and crawling speed is very high. The proposed crawler will improve the efficiency of language specific crawling for Myanmar Language in the future.

REFERENCES

- [1] <http://code.google.com/p/crawler4j/>
- [2] Dr Rajender Nath and Khyati Chopra, (2013)"Web Crawlers: Taxonomy, Issues & Challenges", International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering. Volume 3, Issue 4.
- [3] Trupti V. Udapure, Ravindra D. Kale2, Rajesh C.Dharmik3, (2014)"Study of Web Crawler and its Different Types ", IOSR Journal of Computer Engineering. Volume 16, Issue 1, Ver VI, PP01-05.
- [4] Allan Heydon and Marc Najork, "Mercator: A Scalable, Extensible Web Crawler".

- [5] Eda BayKan, Monka Henzinger, Ingmar Weber, (2008) "Web Pages Language identification based on URLs" .PVLDB '08 , Auchkand, New Zealand.
- [6] Olena Medelyan, Stefan Schulz, Jan Paetzold, Michael Poprar, Kornel Marko "Language Specific and Topic Focused Web Crawling".
- [7] Tomas OLVECKY (2005) "N-gram Based Statistics Aimed at Language Identification", M.Bielikova (Ed). IIT.SRC 2005, pp. 1-7.
- [8] Takayuki Tamura, Kulwadee Somboonviwat and Masaru Kitsuregawa, (2007)"A Method for Language – Specific Web Crawling and Its Evaluation" , Systems and Computers in Japan , Vol.38, No.2.
- [9] Myanmar –English dictionary Department of the Myanmar Language Commission (2011).

AUTHORS

Su Mon Khine received M.C.Sc and B.C. Sc, in Computer Science, from University of Computer Studies, Yangon. She is now PhD candidate in Information and Technology and currently doing research at University of Computer Studies, Yangon. Her research interest includes web crawling, information retrieval, natural language processing and data mining.

Dr. Yadana Thein is now working as an Associate Professor in University of Computer Studies, Yangon (UCSY) under Ministry of Science and Technology, Myanmar. She is particularly interested in Optical Character Recognition, Speech Processing and Networking. She published about 30 papers in workshops, conferences and journals. Currently, she teaches networking subject to under-graduate and post-graduate students. She supervises Master thesis and PhD research candidates in the areas of Image Processing.

